

Effect of exposure to sublethal levels of insecticides on *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* development, growth, and reproduction. Mean \pm SE at 95% confidence.

Cypermethrin had the most effect on pupation and larval survival; pupal survival was not affected, nor was average number of eggs laid per female survivor.

Females from treated larvae appeared normal and oviposition was not affected.

An increase in LF fitness from sublethal doses, therefore, does not account for

insecticide-induced resurgences. Destruction of natural enemies by the insecticides and high recruitment of adults could be possible causes. ■

Integrated pest management – weeds

Agronomic and economic evaluation of herbicides in transplanted rice

S. S. Tomar, Rajasthan Agricultural University, Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Borkhera, Kota 324001 (Raj.), India

Labor constraints can make timely weeding of a transplanted rice crop difficult in southeastern Rajasthan. In 1989 wet season, I studied five herbicides, farmer's method of weeding 20 and 40 d after transplanting (DT), and an unweeded control. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. All herbicides were applied 7 DT on test variety Jaya.

The weed population was 70% grasses, 25% sedges, and 5% broadleaved weeds. Dominant weeds were *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *E. colona*, *Cyperus difformis*, *C. iria*, *Commelina benghalensis*, and *Eclipta prostrata*.

Effect of weed control method on yield and returns to transplanted rice. Kota, India, 1989.

Treatment ^a	Level (kg/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Weed ^a dry weight at harvest (g/m ²)	Net return (\$/ha) over unweeded control	Cost (\$/ha) of weed control	Benefit cost ratio ^b
Anilofos (EC)	0.4	286	4.9	100	112.5	14.6	7.7
Anilofos (EC)	0.6	290	5.1	92	150.0	20.6	7.3
Oxadiazon (EC)	0.4	290	5.2	92	168.8	16.4	10.3
Thiobencarb (G)	1.0	294	5.3	57	187.5	22.8	8.2
Pretilachlor (EC)	0.75	281	4.9	103	112.5	12.2	9.2
Pretilachlor (EC)	1.25	306	5.5	21	225.0	18.5	12.2
Pyrazo sulfuron-ethyl (WP)	0.005	284	5.2	78	168.8	—	—
Pyrazo sulfuron-ethyl (WP)	0.010	279	5.2	83	168.8	—	—
Hand weeding 20 and 40 DT	—	299	5.4	23	206.3	55.2	3.7
Unweeded control	—	201	4.3	206	—	—	—
LSD (0.05)	—	11	0.7	4	—	—	—

^aEC = emulsifiable concentrate, G = granules, WP = wettable powder. Cost: anilofos 30 EC = \$8.9/liter, oxadiazon 25 EC = \$8.5/liter, thiobencarb 10 G = \$2/kg, pretilachlor 50 EC = \$6.3/liter, pyrazo sulfuron-ethyl, not available. Labor required for 2 weedings (20 + 20 DT) and herbicide application (2) in man-days/ha and labor charges = \$1.38/d. ^b Grain price = \$187.5/t.

Rice grain yield was highest (5.5 t/ha) with pretilachlor at 1.25 kg ai/ha (see table). This treatment produced significantly more panicles (306/m²) than other herbicide treatments.

Pretilachlor at 1.25 kg ai/ha had lowest weed dry matter (21 g/m²) and controlled weeds most effectively. Farmer's hand weeding had the lowest benefit:cost ratio; pretilachlor at 1.25 kg ai/ha, the highest. ■